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INSTINCT

D3.1

Initial report on orchestration and control of massive JCAS deployments

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Executive Summary

This report summarizes the initial findings of project INSTINCT work-package 3 dedicated to the orchestration and control of massive joint communication and sensing (JCAS) networks. It constitutes a mid-term report for the work planned in work-package 3, which will be continued. The results presented herein build upon the enablers studied in INSTINCT work-package 2; they are intended to provide candidate technologies for the demonstrations and evaluations to be conducted in work-package 4.

Progress has been made on three different aspect which closely follow the pillars defined in the INSTINCT JCAS system concept: first, we demonstrate several ways in which communication signals can be exploited for the purpose of sensing, yielding opportunistic localization, advanced beam-tracking and ranging, improved GNSS localization, and self-supervised processing methods. These are broadly classified as “communication for sensing.”

Second, we present different ways in which the information sensed in a JCAS system can benefit the communication objective; this includes enhancing coverage prediction through deep learning-based radio maps, and advanced beamforming leveraging location information to mitigate the non-linear effects of power amplifiers. Thus, these contributions fulfill objectives of “sensing for communications.”

Finally, we introduce a multi-objective resource allocation problem where both sensing (direction of arrival estimation) and computing tasks compete for spectral resources in a complex environment. Practical solutions are proposed for a system model including non-terrestrial platforms (drones) and intelligent reflecting surfaces.

Keywords

Massive JCAS, orchestration and control, intelligent surfaces, machine learning.

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1 Introduction

This deliverable describes the initial results obtained within the INSTINCT project on the topic of performing joint communication and sensing (JCAS) efficiently in a complex network, comprising multiple connectivity links, reflective intelligent surfaces (RIS), and mobile terminals evolving in a complex scattering environment. Performing JCAS in this context requires advanced air interface technologies, powerful algorithmic approaches, and powerful orchestration mechanisms.

The results presented herein have been broadly classified according to the three pillars envisioned in INSTINCT, i.e. whether they enhance the network's sensing capabilities based on communication signals ("communicate to sense"), communication capabilities based on sensed information ("sense to communicate"), or whether they enhance the general network performance ("JCAS network intelligence"). A summary of these contributions is given below.

1.1 "Communicate to sense"

The large-scale acquisition of sensed information required to fulfill the INSTINCT vision of a truly intelligent JCAS network relies on the availability of multiple sources of accurate information about the environment. We first focus on four approaches that leverage communication signals to provide or enhance sensing capabilities.

- **Opportunistic ISAC with RIS**

This contribution consists in an opportunistic ISAC approach that leverages the knowledge of RIS configurations used for communication to passively infer user positions. The location is inferred using a learning approach, without interfering with the communication function. These results are detailed in Section 2.

- **Dynamic and Multi-Site Channel Charting for Sensing**

Channel charting is another type of opportunistic approach which leverages long-term channel state information to construct a low-dimensional representation of the radio propagation environment. Being self-supervised, the result is a pseudo-map of the environment which enjoys topological similarity with the true geometric space and consistency across users, time and space. We report on two advances in channel charting, namely multi-site channel charting where the fusion of channel charts obtained by multiple base stations with overlapping coverage is considered, and dynamic channel charting which consists in an online implementation capable of incremental learning with limited memory and computational demands, targeting real-time applications. These results are detailed in Section 3.

- **Hierarchical beam-tracking and ranging**

This work demonstrates how the radiation patterns generated by smart beam design can be exploited efficiently for the purpose of localization. Specifically, a hierarchical beam design is proposed and shown to achieve excellent localization performance while minimizing the spectral overhead associated with localization. These results are detailed in Section 4.

- **AI-based Optimization of 5GNSS for Robust 5G-NR and GNSS Localization**

5GNSS is a framework integrating Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS) with 5G New Radio (5G-NR) to enhance localization accuracy and reliability. Within this context, it is shown how ML techniques can be leveraged to enhance the reliability and accuracy of multi-sensor localization through AI-driven for anchor selection, adaptive data fusion, error correction and anomaly detection mechanisms, contributing to the broader vision of data-driven and adaptive network management. These results are detailed in Section 5.

1.2 “Sense to communicate”

The following two approaches demonstrate specific ways into which sensed information about the environment can be used to enhance the capabilities and the performance of communication networks.

- **Deep Learning for Realistic Coverage Map Predictions**

This work targets the generation of signal strength maps through a deep learning graph neural networks (GNN)-based approach to modeling signal propagation in a 3D real-world environment. This allows for closed-loop network parameter and coverage optimization, enabling adaptive network control in self-optimizing networks scenarios where decisions are continuously refined based on real-time data. These results are detailed in Section 6.

- **Beam-Space Intermodulation Suppression for Line-of-Sight Multiple Input Multiple Output (MIMO) System with Nonlinear Power Amplifiers**

The sensed physical location of the users in a massive MIMO system can be precious information insofar as it allows to limit unintended spurious emissions. In this work, it is demonstrated how location information can be leveraged to spatially mitigate the effects of non-linear beamformed intermodulation distortion through the design of an intermodulation suppression precoder. These results are detailed in Section 7.

1.3 “JCAS Network Intelligence”

The last contribution detailed herein considers the optimal allocation of resources between communication and sensing, with a double objective of communication and sensing.

- **AI-based Optimization for DoA Estimation and Task Offloading in RIS-aided ISAC Systems**

A framework to analyze and optimize the operation of a network incorporating UAV-mounted RISs is introduced, with the goal of achieving an optimal balance between sensing for DoA estimation and communication for task offloading through a statistically robust foundation for DoA estimation. By utilizing non-terrestrial networks, including satellites and aerial platforms, the proposed scheme addresses terrestrial network limitations and facilitates the execution of computationally demanding tasks within tolerable latency. These results are detailed in Section 8.

2 Opportunistic ISAC with RIS

The rapid advancements in wireless communication technologies are pushing towards 6G networks, which demand higher efficiency, adaptability, and integration with sensing capabilities. The RIS technology is one of the key enablers in this evolution, enabling for controlling electromagnetic wave propagation and optimizing the channel for performance improvement.

A particularly transformative concept emerging from this integration is the ISAC, which seeks to unify wireless communication with environmental sensing. Instead of treating communication and sensing as separate domains, ISAC leverages the same network infrastructure for both data transmission, sensing and localization [CDZ24].

However, while the combination of RIS and ISAC is promising, practical implementation faces several challenges. Existing wireless infrastructure was not originally designed for sensing, and adding new capabilities often requires modifications to protocols, dedicated sensing time slots, additional hardware, or computationally expensive processing. This introduces complexity, inefficiencies, and potential disruptions to communication operations. As a result, there is a growing need for a seamless, efficient approach that can integrate sensing functionalities without interfering with the core communication functions of the network.

To overcome these challenges, we propose an opportunistic ISAC approach that leverages pre-existing RIS configurations used for communication to passively infer user positions. This eliminates the need for additional sensing operations, making localization seamless, low-power, and fully compatible with existing wireless networks. This contribution is detailed in the following subsections, further information can be found in the related publication [EDR24].

2.1 RIS configuration

The configuration of RIS is a complex problem that requires joint optimization of the BS precoder and RIS settings to maximize the desired KPI. Several optimization strategies exist, including gradient optimization [PZZ22], alternating optimization [YXS20], ML-based approaches [EAS23], and coherent path maximization [BOL19]. However, RIS configuration depends on the channel conditions between the BS, RIS, and UE, which are influenced by their relative positions.

Figure 2.1: Example of a communication scenario where the BS operates in the far-field and the UE in the near-field of the RIS, illustrating the corresponding wavefront spatially sampled at the RIS elements and the resulting RIS configuration.

A clarifying example is provided in Figure 2.1: the BS signal forms a planar wavefront at the RIS, while the UE signal forms a spherical one. The RIS configuration is determined based on the phase distribution of these wavefronts to align direct and reflected signal paths. Hence, when operating for communication purposes—regardless of the specific application (e.g., channel enhancement or gain flooring)—the location of the communicating devices directly influences the resulting RIS configuration. Specifically, the configuration adapts to the direction of arrival (departure) of the signal for a far-field device and to both the direction of arrival (departure) and distance for a near-field device.

Figure 2.2 RIS configurations from [ADS22](left-hand side), from [BOL19](center), and alternate optimization algorithm from [MSG20](right-hand side).

Figure 2.2 represents a comparison of the RIS configurations obtained using three different optimization strategies, demonstrating that similar configurations emerge regardless of the optimization approach used.

We leverage this characteristic to design a localization strategy that, based solely on the configuration of one or multiple RIS, opportunistically recovers the position of connected devices. Unlike state-of-the-art localization solutions, our strategy does not require time-of-arrival (ToA) information, power measurements, or specific operations at the RIS—such as selecting particular configurations to scan the surrounding area and comparing received signals at the BS to locate the target. This approach offers key technical advantages: (i) it does not interfere with communication enhancement operations at the RIS, and (ii) it does not require

cooperation with the BS or UEs, such as performing channel measurements. We detail the proposed localization strategy in the following subsection.

2.2 Opportunistic ISAC solution

We propose an opportunistic framework, dubbed COLoRIS, that leverages RIS configuration patterns to estimate user positions with high accuracy. COLoRIS employs a deep neural network (DNN) to directly reconstruct the position of a UE based on the RIS configuration used to serve it. This approach ensures adaptability to different environments and propagation conditions without requiring significant modifications.

Figure 2.3: A schematic representation of COLoRIS, showing the RIS configuration as input, the internal estimators, and the user position and accuracy as output.

The workflow of COLoRIS is depicted in Figure 2.3. The system operates alongside the RIS-aided communication infrastructure without interfering with ongoing transmissions. It processes through a Deep Neural Network (DNN) the RIS configurations forwarded by the controller and opportunistically generates position estimations. This design enables seamless adaptation to dynamic environments, particularly in high-mobility scenarios, by continuously updating location estimates as new RIS configurations become available.

The accuracy estimation process is based on the relationship between localization precision and the spatial gradient of the selected RIS configurations. More in detail, the achievable accuracy is linked to how the RIS configurations change with respect to the user's position [EDR24]. These changes can be approximated by computing the gradient of the RIS configuration with respect to the estimated UE location. If small changes in the estimated position result in minimal variations in the RIS configuration then the derived position information is less precise. Conversely, if small changes in lead to significant variations in the RIS configuration, the localization accuracy improves. Nonetheless, this requires knowledge on the RIS optimization process executed by the controller, which might not always be accessible, and could limit the practical applicability of the accuracy estimation if direct access to RIS configurations is restricted. However, the relationship between user position and configuration can be obtained through a secondary DNN that approximates the RIS configuration process.

Training can be conducted independently using simulated data or collaboratively with the communication infrastructure by leveraging existing localization sources. Additionally, a continuous training approach incorporating external data would allow the system to iteratively refine its accuracy.

2.3 Results and outcomes

To assess performance, we consider a $100 \times 100 \text{ m}^2$ test area with UE locations distributed regularly in it, a single square RIS with 441 elements serving a BS equipped with an ULA of 16 antennas. The RIS configuration has 1 bit of phase quantization, with phase configuration that can be either 0 or π . The RIS is configured for serving one user at a time with configuration optimized through the coherent path approach described in [ADS22]. We include the effect of noisy channels by adding a gaussian error to the phase of selected RIS configuration with variance equal to $\pi/6$. We employ a DNN comprising 441 input neurons, hence, we process the entire RIS configuration vector, followed by 2 fully connected hidden layers of 100 neurons each, and a 2 neurons output layer providing the UE coordinates of the estimation.

Figure 2.4: Location estimation performance of in the considered area.

Figure 2.4 depicts the error obtained for 100 randomly chosen test points (left hand side), and a histogram over the complete testing set (right-hand side). The average error across the testing set is 5.04m.

Figure 2.5 Prediction errors of COLoRIS expressed in polar coordinates relative to the RIS-user distance, including the error median and interquartile range (IQR).

Figure 2.5 highlights the behavior of radial and angular errors against the relative UE-RIS distance, both graphs include the data points, the median and the interquartile range obtained with a moving average of 100 samples.

Figure 2.6 True localization error in comparison with the prediction of COLoRIS accuracy estimation module.

Finally, Figure 2.6 shows the performance in accuracy estimation, by showing on the left-hand side the actual estimation accuracy, in the center the estimation error predicted by assuming knowledge of the RIS optimization process and by direct computation of the RIS configuration gradient. Differently, for the NN approach, we employ a DNN that processes the RIS configuration, comprising two hidden layers of 100 neurons and producing the magnitude of the error as output. The dataset used for training and testing this DNN is created from the test set of the first DNN by associating each RIS configuration with the corresponding inference error magnitude. Results confirm the ability of COLoRIS in the accuracy prediction task.

2.4 Considerations on deployment scenario and scalability

The proposed ISAC approach enables the extraction of location information from RIS configurations. RIS are optimized and operated for communication purposes only. This ensures that the localization process does not interfere with the communication functionality of the network. In other words, it operates opportunistically to localize. When multiple RISs are involved in serving a single user, their location estimations can be combined to potentially enhance overall localization accuracy. Indeed, the simultaneous generation of an estimation and an associated

error provides a statistical characterization of the estimation, facilitating the integration of information from several RISs, or from other localization methods, such as GPS or cellular localization. This aligns with cooperative localization techniques [WLW09].

2.5 Conclusions

This contribution leverages the controlled-reflective properties of RIS to achieve accurate localization opportunistically. In particular, it employs non-intrusive, localization-agnostic RIS configurations, optimized for communication purposes only, to perform localization. This removes the need for extra sensing steps, enabling a localization approach that integrates smoothly with current wireless systems.

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3 Channel Charting for Sensing and RIS control

Channel charting (CC) is an unsupervised learning technique that utilizes channel state information (CSI) to construct a low-dimensional representation of the radio propagation environment through dimensionality reduction (DR) [SM18]. It leverages the latent physical and geometrical information embedded in the CSI to extract a lower-dimensional representation, which is easier to exploit. CC can be seen as a building box for multiple applications including predictive radio resource management and beam management, proximity detection, context awareness for digital twin applications, geofencing, and improving localization [FG23].

Many applications of CC require applying DR to a large number of CSI samples, which are measured at high sampling rates (typically around 100 samples per second) by each base station (BS). BSs often have limited computational and storage resources, especially for auxiliary tasks like CC, as their primary function is to manage telecommunications. Since it is desirable to apply CC over data collected over long durations (potentially weeks or months), it is reasonable to assume that the total amount of CSI that will be acquired is a priori unbounded. Consequently, it is not feasible to store indefinitely all the observed CSI samples. This calls for the development of dynamic, online channel charting algorithms. Original results on the topic of online CC with limited storage have been obtained in INSTINCT; they have been published in [VG25] and are detailed in Section 3.2.

Furthermore, in a radio access network scenario, it is also typical for one UE to be within the coverage area of multiple base stations (or access point); in this context, it is desirable to produce a channel chart representation which is consistent across base stations, despite the user having completely different CSI when seen from either base station. The problem of representation alignment in multi-site CC has been addressed as well in INSTINCT, with results published in [VG24] and reported in Section 3.1.

3.1 Multi-site Channel Charting

While multipoint channel charting considers efficient ways of fusing the features acquired by multiple access points while computing a *single* channel chart in a centralized manner, we introduced the *multi-site* channel charting problem whereby multiple base stations generate their own channel charts, while their coverage areas partially overlap (see Figure 3.1). The objective is to learn a set of mappings from the individual channel charts produced at each base station to a common, unified channel chart; these mappings should ensure that the pseudo-positions of users within overlapping coverage areas and “seen” from the respective base stations, match in the unified channel chart.

Figure 3.1: Problem summary with 2 base stations BS1 and BS2, with overlapping coverage maps G_1 and G_2 , and ambient CSI spaces C_1 and C_2 , respectively. Ambient spaces are divided into subsets containing samples from geometric positions shared by both stations (S_1 and S_2), and those containing samples unique to each base station (U_1 and U_2). C_1 and C_2 undergo separate dimensionality reduction through functions f_1 and f_2 , yielding channel charts $f_1(C_1)$ and $f_2(C_2)$. Manifold alignment is performed through transformations g_1 and g_2 which are applied to the respective channel charts, yielding a final chart for each base station, embedded in a common unified chart $g_1(f_1(C_1)) \cup g_2(f_2(C_2))$.

We introduced several methods to align the latent spaces at each base station into a common latent space, effectively performing the fusion of multiple channel charts:

- Cell alignment: in this approach, the g_i are affine functions. A joint objective function combining distance learning (charting) and Wasserstein (optimal transport, OT) distance between the chart points representing the same data from the point of view of multiple base stations is optimized.
- Cell alignment with independent OT: This approach is similar to the previous one, except that the optimization is split in two steps: channel charts are first computed independently at each BS through optimization of the mapping functions f_i (see Fig. 3.1). Subsequently, the manifold alignment functions g_i are optimized to minimize the Wasserstein distance between the chart points representing the same data from the point of view of multiple base stations.
- Cell topology alignment: This approach consists of jointly training the composition of the local mapping functions and the alignment functions $h_1 = g_1 \circ f_1$ and $h_2 = g_2 \circ f_2$ and using one single transformation model $g = g_1 = g_2$ to align the CC of both base stations with respect to their coverage maps.
- Cell topology alignment with independent OT: Like Cell alignment with independent OT, but the optimization is performed in two sequential steps.
- Joint Sample and Cell alignment: This approach consists of training h_1 and h_2 jointly and learning one transformation model per BS to align the CC of both base stations with respect to their coverage maps. In addition, to promote proximity among the

representations of corresponding samples from different BS in the shared coverage area within the final common CC, we minimize their difference.

- **Sample alignment:** This method is similar to the previous one, except that we ignore the optimal transport part of the objective. As a result, this approach ignores coverage map data and relies solely on associating two samples from different base stations, both generated by the same user at the same location.

We benchmarked the proposed approaches and compared their performance in terms of the classical dimensionality reduction metrics using measured data, as well as their degree of distributedness. The proposed approaches were compared according to classical dimensionality reduction metrics: Trustworthiness (T), continuity (C), and Kruskal stress (KS) between the chart and the 2D positions where each CSI sample was acquired (this ground truth information would not be available in practice). We also considered several alignment metrics based on the intersection-over-union (IoU) of two polygons A and B metric, denoted by $\text{IoU}(A,B)$. We compute IoU_C as $\text{IoU}(A,B)$ where A and B are the convex hulls of common coverage areas as seen on the common chart based on CSI from different base stations; higher values indicate a greater overlap between common coverage areas. We also evaluate $1 - \text{IoU}_{BS}$, where the IoU_{BS} metric considers the IoU between CC positions of CSI samples that are not acquired by both BS and the ones that are; higher values (less overlap) are better. Finally, we compute the fraction of samples closer than the true match (FOSCTTM) metric introduced in [CF023], which indicates the fraction of samples which are incorrectly placed closer than the true match (defined as perfect alignment in the unified chart between CSI measured at different BSs) by the chart alignment algorithm (lower is better). Numerical results are reported in Table 3.1.

Method	\mathcal{G}_1	$\mathcal{G}_1 \cap \mathcal{G}_2$	$\mathcal{G}_1 \setminus \mathcal{G}_2$	$\mathcal{G}_2 \setminus \mathcal{G}_1$	$\mathcal{S}_1 \leftrightarrow \mathcal{S}_2$	$\text{IoU}_C \uparrow$	$1 - \text{IoU}_{BS} \uparrow$	FOSCTTM \downarrow	T \uparrow	KS \downarrow	WD \downarrow
Centralized Model	×	×	×	×	×	76.42 ± 3.97	45.97 ± 2.97	34.15 ± 1.60	72.99 ± 0.85	<i>0.48 ± 0.01</i>	5.89 ± 3.12
No Alignment	×	×	×	×	×	29.46 ± 16.49	43.82 ± 2.81	50.25 ± 3.55	<i>74.81 ± 4.94</i>	0.54 ± 0.02	5.23 ± 0.45
Cell Alignment	✓	×	×	×	×	28.41 ± 12.30	36.89 ± 3.67	49.74 ± 3.02	72.51 ± 3.24	60.55 ± 0.07	0.54 ± 0.13
Cell Alignment Independent OT	✓	×	×	×	×	22.18 ± 3.44	44.69 ± 2.36	51.09 ± 1.91	74.10 ± 1.33	0.58 ± 0.05	<i>0.47 ± 0.07</i>
Cell Topology Alignment	×	✓	✓	✓	×	<i>71.76 ± 10.10</i>	76.62 ± 6.05	49.68 ± 1.49	75.27 ± 1.21	0.46 ± 0.02	0.28 ± 0.09
Cell Topology Alignment Independent OT	×	✓	✓	✓	×	29.34 ± 12.09	39.76 ± 2.32	48.50 ± 5.62	74.20 ± 2.06	0.53 ± 0.05	0.84 ± 0.34
Joint Sample and Cell Alignment	✓	×	×	×	✓	55.08 ± 14.40	74.16 ± 5.76	<i>40.23 ± 1.70</i>	<i>74.14 ± 1.43</i>	0.52 ± 0.02	0.986 ± 0.003
Sample Alignment	×	×	×	×	✓	11.62 ± 8.34	60.06 ± 8.32	49.95 ± 0.89	68.11 ± 3.28	0.69 ± 0.03	5.32 ± 0.15

Table 3.1: Alignment and dimensionality reduction results of the different compared approaches. Best results in bold, second-best in italics. $\mathcal{S}_1 \leftrightarrow \mathcal{S}_2$ denotes the use of the sample-by-sample correspondence between the elements of \mathcal{S}_1 and \mathcal{S}_2 , which entails extra communication overhead.

We observe that the best overall performing method in terms of local structure preservation is Cell Topology Alignment, with improvements of T and KS, often reducing the variability. Its refined alignment process aligns unique coverage zones with each other and common coverage areas accordingly, for each BS, enhancing T by minimizing the occurrence of distant samples becoming neighbors in the final CC. This also leads to a decrease in KS (distance preservation).

Evaluating local structure preservation metrics on the final CC shows that samples from both BS1 and BS2 can be neighbors, especially within common coverage areas, further improving local structure preservation compared to individual BS measurements. Second, it is noteworthy that the Cell Topology Alignment model stands out as the best one based on global structure preservation. This superiority can be attributed to two main factors. Firstly, methods that align

CCs to geometric coverage maps have an inherent advantage because the Wasserstein distance is an OT distance. This alignment to geometric coverage maps has practical benefits, such as enabling real coordinate localization and proximity detection of users. Secondly, Cell Topology Alignment operate on zones instead of aligning each CC with the entire coverage maps of their corresponding BS. This approach effectively brings CC samples closer to their GT positions, despite the equal weights assumption.

Figure 3.2: Combined best final channel charts for the top 4 best performing methods over five repetitions. (a) Cell Topology Alignment, (b) Joint Sample and Cell Alignment, (c) No Alignment, (d) Cell Alignment with Independent OT.

Figure 3.2 depicts the combined channel charts obtained for some of the previously described approaches. Inspection of the results show that Cell Topology Alignment emerges as the most overall effective method for CC alignment: it outperforms other methods significantly with lower variability. Notably, its performance closely resembles that of the Centralized Model. The superiority of Cell Topology Alignment comes from its explicit alignment of individual and shared coverage areas with associated geometrical maps, unlike other methods. Moreover, its outperformance over Joint Sample and Cell Topology Alignment is due to the latter's less refined alignment across entire coverage areas rather than treating them separately. This refinement is critical as uniform weights assumed in the OT problem can lead to mismatches, emphasizing the significance of Cell Topology Alignment.

Joint Sample and Cell Alignment outperforms Cell Topology Alignment in FOSCTTM. Yet, for localization and distance measurement, the discontinuities between BS coverage areas observed for Joint Sample and Cell Alignment are problematic, unlike with Cell Topology Alignment (smooth CC transitions are preferable to avoid abrupt user zone changes). However, the observed enhancement in terms of FOSCTTM with Joint Sample and Cell Alignment compared to Cell Topology Alignment is noteworthy. In shared coverage areas, each measurement has two representations (one per BS). Thus, it is crucial for these CC coordinates to align closely. The reduced FOSCTTM of Joint Sample and Cell Alignment indicates that its aligned CC results in fewer false positives in common areas. This means that for a given point in

the shared coverage area in the CC of one BS, there are fewer points from the other BS closer to it than its true corresponding point, compared to other methods.

Finally, despite No Alignment obtaining the CC of each BS independently, it still shows noticeable alignment, occasionally outperforming other methods relying on OT or distance minimization. This highlights Channel Charting’s inherent capability to map radio environments; shared coverage areas likely have similar propagation environments, leading to similar CC.

3.2 Dynamic Channel Charting

The problem of online CC with limited storage memory was formulated by introducing a dual memory architecture based on a long-term memory acting as the core-set reservoir, and a short-term buffer which can store incoming samples during model updates and memory updates. We introduced several memory update strategies suitable for the contrastive learning goal of triplet-based CC as introduced in [FD21]. The global considered architecture is depicted in Figure 3.3.

Figure 3.3: Problem Summary. Our framework involves steps to periodically update long-term memory and train the model with new data from the buffer. At time t , the model is trained with the dataset in the combined (short-term buffer and long-term) memory. Each sample serves as an anchor for triplet learning, with positive and negative examples (indicated by the red and green arrows in the first block).

The work addressed the update mechanism of the core-set stored in the long-term memory. Specifically, the following approaches were considered:

- Random selection: This straightforward yet naive approach to online sample selection involves randomly determining whether to retain each incoming sample from the buffer

in memory according to a fixed (non-data-dependent) probability. If the sample is retained, another sample in memory is randomly chosen for removal to make space. This approach suffers from catastrophic forgetting.

- Reservoir sampling (RS): This memory update strategy operates on individual samples, without the concept of a buffer. It is a data-independent probabilistic approach which enables an online implementation of a uniform random sample selection policy.
- Similarity-based Subset – Second Closest Neighbor (SimS-SCN): The main objective of this data-dependent approach is to minimize the similarity between samples in the long-term memory to encourage diversity within the memory set. Similarity is defined using a postulated feature-space distance. We enhanced the greedy SimS algorithm from [TGT23] by introducing a more robust replacement strategy consisting in adjusting the selection criteria for samples to be removed from memory. Our idea involves prioritizing the removal of the sample with the closest second nearest neighbor (i.e. the most redundant sample). We refer to this method as SimS-SCN, where SCN stands for “Second Closest Neighbor.”
- Max-Min Point Spacing (MMPS): This approach is similar to SimS, with the difference that we use the learned distance in lieu of the sample-space distance to update the long-term memory.
- Loss-Driven Ranking Sample Selection (LDRSS): This approach is comparable to the offline supervised continual learning method discussed in [ZHC22]. However, our method introduces a loss function-based unsupervised online CL framework. The primary objective is to enhance the difficulty of the samples stored in memory by maximizing their loss function, based on the intuition that samples with higher loss tend to be more informative to the model than those with smaller loss. This strategy promotes diversity and complexity within the memory set. Again, a greedy approximate solution is used to adapt the algorithm to the online setting.
- Gradient-Driven Ranking Sample Selection (GDRSS): This approach is comparable to the online CL method from [ALG19]. However, our method employs a direct gradient-based scoring mechanism to select samples from the buffer for long-term memory retention, since samples with larger gradients tend to be more informative for model learning. The primary goal is to retain the samples that contribute most significantly to reaching a local minimum. For the online setting, a greedy algorithm to find an approximate solution.

The above approaches were evaluated using two datasets from the DICHASUS platform of the University of Stuttgart [EG22], specifically cf-02 for training, and cf-03 for testing. Both datasets cover the same indoor industrial environment, where a robot equipped with an omnidirectional antenna traversed an L-shaped area. CSI was measured between the robot and four access points (APs), each with eight antennas. We biased towards a heavily non-stationary sampling process, in order to model the kind of non-stationarity expected in real-life long-term CIS collection, with users remaining still between periods of movement. This non-stationarity is a particularly difficult scenario for channel charting, as the observed process cannot be assumed to be drawn independently from a stationary distribution, and the online setting does not allow to interleave the data within the dataset to make it appear stationary. Numerical results are presented in Table

3.2. It can be observed that GDRSS dominates the performance in terms of neighborhood-preservation metrics (T and C), while MMPS yields the best KS metric.

Method	T \uparrow	C \uparrow	KS \downarrow
Offline	73.90 ± 1.12	82.83 ± 1.27	0.61 ± 0.02
RS	87.62 ± 2.39	89.46 ± 1.80	0.47 ± 0.07
Random	83.32 ± 1.10	88.97 ± 1.27	0.41 ± 0.07
SimS-SCN	88.50 ± 0.76	91.85 ± 0.48	0.32 ± 0.02
MMPS	88.85 ± 1.23	92.12 ± 0.79	0.31 ± 0.03
LDRSS	87.20 ± 1.66	90.97 ± 0.50	0.35 ± 0.02
GDRSS	90.06 ± 0.67	92.99 ± 0.32	0.34 ± 0.03

Table 3.2: Model performance based on the replay strategy.

Illustrations of the obtained channel charts are depicted in Figure 3.4. The ground-truth location of the samples retained in long-term memory after playing the whole dataset is depicted as well, illustrating the fact that GDRSS effectively compensates for the sampling bias in the dataset.

Figure 3.4: Examples of channel charts, obtained respectively through RS and GDRSS are depicted in (b) and (d); the ground-truth sampling positions corresponding to the samples retained in the long-term memory are respectively depicted in Figs. (a) and (c). The (top-heavy) sampling bias introduced to model non-stationarity is visible on Fig. (a), while it is successfully compensated by the GDRSS approach in Fig. (c).

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4 Hierarchical beam-tracking and ranging

So far, wireless communications have been operating in the far-field of the radiating elements. However, with the increase of the operating frequency the size of the elements can be reduced, which allows for the design of antennas and RISs with the same size as modern antennas, but with significantly more elements. As a result, at relatively small distances, the operation moves from the far- to the near-field. With both antennas and RISs the distance where the transition occurs can be adjusted through the footprint of the active or illuminated elements. Moreover, operation in the near-field enables the implementation of new functionalities such as beam-focusing, while the ability to adjust the distance at which the transition from the near- to the far-field occurs, allows the control of aspects such as the maximum distance where beam-focusing can be performed and the size of the focal area. Next, we present the concept of hierarchical range-angle localization that takes advantage of the beamforming and beam-focusing functionalities.

4.1 System model

Figure 4.1: System model. (a) The TX (either an LAA or an AP with a LIS) performs beamforming or beam-focusing towards the RX. (b) The footprint of the TX beam (at $z=0$) has tapered amplitude that reaches zero within the TX panel. The footprint evolves into a beam that propagates on the xz -plane, according to Eq. 1 as depicted schematically in (a).

Localization based on beam-focusing takes advantage of the property of focused beams to concentrate the power to a small area called focal area. The concept of this method is that the TX generates focused beams towards multiple locations and estimates in which one the RX is in. The focal area whose center is closer to the RX is the one that provides the maximum power to the RX and therefore signifies its location. The TX can be an LAA, in which case it generates the focused beam towards the RX, or alternatively an access point (AP) that illuminates the LIS, which in turn focuses the power of the incident beam to the location of the RX. The system model is shown in Figure 4.1, where the beam-footprint at the TX is depicted with a density plot. For beam-focusing-based localization to work, the size of the focal areas must be known and ideally adjustable. Here,

the equations to adjust the size of the focal areas are derived. In [DSA24] it was shown that for beam-focusing taking place on the xz-plane with a Gaussian footprint contained entirely in the TX panel, as is our case here, the power density distribution of the focused beam is given by

$$S_r(x, z) = \frac{2P_t}{\pi w_x w_y} \frac{1}{\sqrt{\left(1 - \frac{z}{f_0 \cos \theta_r}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{2z}{k w_y^2 \cos \theta_r}\right)^2}} \times \frac{1}{\sqrt{\left(1 - \frac{z}{f_0 \cos \theta_r}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{2z}{k w_x^2 \cos \theta_r}\right)^2}} \left(\frac{1}{\cos \theta_r}\right)^4 \times \exp \left[-\frac{2(x \cos \theta_r - z \sin \theta_r)^2}{w_x^2 \left(\left(\cos \theta_r - \frac{z}{f_0}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{2z}{k w_x^2 \cos^2 \theta_r}\right)^2 \right)} \right] \quad (4.1)$$

Where P_t is the transmitted power, w_x , and w_y are the horizontal and vertical beam-footprint radii, θ_r is the angle of the beam's direction on the xz-plane, f_0 is the input wavefront curvature of the beam (i.e. at the LAA/LIS), and k is the wavenumber. In the case where the TX is an LIS, $w_x = \frac{w_y}{\cos(\theta_i)}$, where θ_i is the incident beam angle. Note that when $f_0 \rightarrow \infty$ the wavefront becomes planar, and the TX essentially performs beamforming. The received power at the RX location using Eq. (1) is given by

$$P_r = S_r A_r, \quad (4.2)$$

where $A_r = G_r \lambda^2 / 4\pi$, and G_r are the effective aperture and the antenna gain of the receiver and λ is the wavelength. For a certain value of f_0 along $\theta_r = 0$, with which the horizontal and vertical footprint radii become $w_x = w_y \equiv w$, the maximum power is achieved at focal distance

$$d_f = \frac{f_0}{(f_0/z_R)^2 + 1}, \quad (4.3)$$

where $z_R = kw^2/2$ is the Rayleigh length. For relatively large footprints with which $z_R \gg f_0$, $d_f \approx f_0$. The focal distance d_f is the distance between the TX and the center of the focal elliptical area, whose major axis is along the beam direction [WJZ20]. Using Eq. (4.2) the major radius of the 3dB focal area along $\theta_r = 0$ is calculated as

$$r_{max} = \frac{f_0}{(f_0/z_R)^2 + 1} \frac{f_0}{z_R}. \quad (4.4)$$

The size and location of the 3dB elliptical focal areas are required for properly dividing the radial distance to achieve the desired localization resolution, which is determined by the size of the ellipse along the TX-RX direction, i.e. the major radius r_{max} . Note that d_f and r_{max} are controlled entirely by f_0 and w (the latter through z_R) and, hence, the radial distance can be divided into as many ellipses as desired. According to Eq. (4.4), for a fixed w the size of the focal area increases with increasing f_0 , and, hence, to form ellipses of equal size that guarantee uniform resolution, it is required that each beam is formed with a different footprint. For $z_R \gg f_0$, the footprint practically changes proportionally to f_0 for fixed r_{max} (see Eq. (4.4)). By solving Eqs. (4.3) and (4.4) for f_0 , the input wavefront curvature for a focal area of focal distance, d_f , and major radius, r_{max} , is

$$f_0 = d_f \left(\left(\frac{r_{max}}{d_f} \right)^2 + 1 \right) \quad (4.5)$$

Moreover, by solving for w , the radius of the beam-footprint on the TX for the same focal area is

$$w = \sqrt{2 \frac{r_{max}^2 + d_f^2}{kr_{max}}} \quad (4.6)$$

After defining the desired localization resolution, i.e. a set of focal distances and major radii, accounting for all ellipses along the direction of the RX, Eqs. (4.5) and (4.6) are used to calculate the corresponding parameters f_0 and w for each individual focal area. These parameters are used in Eq. (4.1) to generate the respective focal areas and implement the focusing-based localization algorithm.

4.2 Hierarchical range-angle localization

The ability to concentrate the power of the transmitted or reflected beam to a small area is ideal for localization applications. However, a small focal area makes searching in the entire area of interest slow and requires a prohibitively large overhead. Therefore, it can be assisted by hierarchical beam-tracking. The whole procedure can be split into two phases as presented in Figure 4.2. In Phase 1 a binary tree-structured codebook is utilized to partition the area of interest into angular-based sectors with beamforming. Similarly, in Phase 2 a binary tree structured codebook is utilized to partition the area of interest into distance-wise with beam-focusing along the direction specified by Phase 1. The purpose of both phases is to estimate the angle and distance of the RX with adjustable resolution.

Figure 4.2: Concept of the proposed localization algorithm. With the Phase 1 codebook, the TX estimates the RX direction with the use of beamforming by selecting the correct beam, and with the Phase 2 codebook, it estimates the TX-RX distance with beam-focusing by selecting the correct focal area. The schematics of beams in Phase 1 and focal areas in Phase 2 represent all codewords that are stored at each level of the corresponding codebook. The dark-toned versions of the beam/focal areas represent example codewords that are used in the hierarchical approach, to locate the RX shown in this example.

In phase 1, beam-tracking is performed with beamforming through the RIS, in order to estimate the direction of the RX with respect to the RIS. In phase 2, ranging is performed with beam-focusing through the RIS, to estimate the distance of the RX from the RIS, along the direction identified in phase 1. With information about both the angle and distance, the location of the RX is fully determined. Both phases follow a hierarchical and binary tree structure. Essentially, the area of interest (e.g. the semi-infinite space in front of the RIS) is represented by a polar grid, with the RIS at its origin. In phase 1 the angular sector where the user is located is identified and in phase 2 the radial distance of the RX is estimated within the available resolution of the focal spot. The beams utilized in each phase comprise the respective codebook. The search can be accelerated with prediction. In the absence of prediction, all codebook levels are utilized to find the user, although the starting level may be different in each phase. However, with enough samples about the location of the RX, the TX can start predicting the next location of the user in relation to the location of the RIS and scan a small area around the predicted location using both phases but with fewer number of hierarchical levels. Prediction of the user's location in the next timeslot enables the TX to start the search from a higher hierarchical level in both phases, resulting in reduced overhead and required time to find the RX location.

4.2.1 Phase 1: Beamforming (beam-training)

The beam-training process in this work follows the binary tree search process, and utilizes a beamforming codebook, of $L_t = \log_2 N$ levels, where N is the total number of elements of an antenna array along the x-direction, where beam-steering takes place. Since the codebook is binary tree-structured, the number of codewords in each level is 2^{l_t} , where $l_t = 1, 2, \dots, L_t$ is the current codebook level. In this work, a codebook similar to the one introduced in [Sayeed2010] is used to fill the levels of a hierarchical codebook, which is here referred to as beamforming (Bfr) codebook, i.e. the phase of the TX array elements in each codebook level is the same as in [SB10]. However, in this work the amplitude of the TX array elements is tapered to form a Gaussian distribution, which leads to the formation of Gaussian beams, as described by Eq. (6.1). The number of active elements is adjusted through the footprint radius, which in the case of an LIS, depends on the antenna beam-width of the access point (AP). Therefore, it is necessary to translate the number of active elements to footprint size. For example, $N \times N$ active antenna elements correspond to beam-footprint radius $w_x \approx \frac{N}{2} d_x$ and $w_y \approx \frac{N}{2} d_y$, where d_x , and d_y are the horizontal and vertical dimensions of each element.

The beam-training process is as follows. The TX generates beams using the two codewords of the first level of the codebook. Then the RX estimates the received power with both beams and sends the information to the TX as feedback. The direction of the RX is the direction of the beam that offers the highest power at the RX. The TX then generates beams using the two codewords of the next level that correspond to the codeword with which the RX was found and estimate again the direction of the RX. This process is repeated until the highest level of the codebook is reached. The number of codewords in each level, is 2^{l_t} , where $l_t = 1, 2, \dots, L_t$ is the current codebook level. With this process, the exhaustive search is carried out with 2^{L_t} codewords, instead of 2^{L_t} which would be the case if only the highest codebook level with the narrowest beams was used in an exhaustive search.

4.2.2 Phase 2: Beam-focusing (ranging)

The ranging process also follows the binary tree search process. The first step is to generate a beam-focusing (Bfc) codebook, of L_r levels that is used to form the desired focal areas. Similarly to the Bfr codebook, the number of focal areas per level is 2^{l_r} , where $l_r = 1, 2, \dots, L_r$ is the current codebook level. For example, the first codebook level stores the weights of two focal areas, the second, the weights of four focal areas, etc. In order to generate the Bfc codebook, assuming that the maximum distance in the area of interest is d_0 , the area of interest is divided into two smaller are distance-wise. Then each area is again divided into two smaller areas, and this process is repeated until the desired resolution is r , which phase is determined by the major radius of the focal area, r_{max} .

Figure 4.3. Focal areas of a codebook with two levels for $d_0 = 5\text{m}$, with (a) $\alpha = 0.25$, (b) $\alpha = 0.375$, and (c) $\alpha = 0.5$.

The focal distances of the focal areas in the codebook can be calculated as

$$d_f(1_r, i) = \frac{d_f(1, 1)}{2^{1_r-1}} m_i, \quad (4.7)$$

where $d_f(1, 1) = d_0/4$ is the focal distance for the first codeword in the first codebook level, d_0 is the maximum distance from the TX in the area of interest, $i = 1, 2, \dots, 2^{1_r}$ is the codeword index. Moreover, $m_i = 1, 3, 5, \dots, M$ is a set of 2^{1_r} numbers that includes all the odd numbers from 1 to $M = 2^{1_r+1} - 1$. The major radii of the focal areas can be calculated as,

$$r_{\max}(1_r) = \alpha \frac{d_0}{2^{1_r-1}}, \quad (4.8)$$

where $\alpha \in [0.25, 0.5]$ is the focal area overlapping coefficient. For $\alpha \leq 0.25$, adjacent focal areas are formed without overlapping. Specifically, the two adjacent ellipses meet at a single point, as shown in Figure 4.3 (a). Lower values of α result in gaps between the 3dB focal areas, while with higher values the overlap between the focal areas is increased, as demonstrated in (b), where $\alpha = 0.375$. Moreover, the value $\alpha = 0.5$ marks the limit, after which more than two adjacent focal areas overlap, as shown in (c). If the RX is inside two focal areas at the same time, the algorithm can choose either one and continue refining the estimated TX-RX distance without problem. However, with values of α , that make more than two focal areas to overlap, the resolution of each focal area is reduced substantially as the focal areas become unnecessarily large. By controlling both d_0 , and α , it is possible to control r_{\max} (see Eq. (4.8)), and consequently, the resolution of Phase 2. All focal areas within the Bfc codebook are formed along the direction of the RX based

on the Bfr codebook in Phase 1, with the same d_f , and r_{max} . To generate the focal areas for the codebook, the output of Eqs. (4.7), and (4.8) is inserted to Eqs. (4.5), and (4.6).

4.3 Performance evaluation with static users

Next, the performance of the proposed algorithm is evaluated with Monte-Carlo simulations of 10^6 RX locations in two scenarios with static users. The locations of the RXs are randomly generated with the uniform distribution in both angle and distance in an area that extends 25° to the left and right of the TX broadside. The minimum distance of the RXs from the surface where the TX is placed, is 10 cm. In scenario 1, the maximum distance d_0 is 5 m from the center of the TX, while in scenario 2 it is 10 m. The frequency of operation is 150 GHz, the spacing of the array elements is $d_x = d_y = \lambda/2$, and the transmitted power is 30 dBm. Moreover, the antenna gain of the receiver is $G_r = 20$ dB, and the size of the array is much larger than the largest beam-footprint required by the codebook, which is achieved with either the highest level of the Bfr codebook, or the first level of the Bfc codebook. Furthermore, the focal areas are formed with $\alpha = 0.3$.

Codebook level	r_{max} $d_0 = 5$	r_{max} $d_0 = 10$
1	1.5 m	3 m
2	0.75 m	1.5 m
3	0.375 m	0.75 m
4	0.187 m	0.375 m
5	0.093 m	0.187 m
6	0.046 m	0.093 m
7	0.023 m	0.046 m
8	0.011 m	0.023 m

Table 4.1: Major radius of each beam-focusing codebook level for $d_0 = 5m$, and $10m$, with $\alpha = 0.3$.

In Table 1, the resolution, r_{max} of all Bfc codebook levels is presented for the two scenarios. In Phase 1, the beams of the beamforming codebook in level 1 span the entire $(-90^\circ, +90^\circ)$ range. However, as the area of interest is smaller, Phase 1 starts from the 4th codebook level, where the beams are narrower and only the beams that cover the angular range of the area of interest are

used. As the proposed localization is hierarchical, in Phase 1, the TX utilizes all codebook levels from the 4th level and up of the Bfr codebook using the binary tree approach to find the direction of the RX. In Phase 2, the TX uses all codebook levels of the Bfc codebook starting from the 2nd level in the direction estimated in Phase 1 to find the TX-RX distance. In both scenarios, the Bfr codebook in Phase 1 is composed of 10 levels, and the Bfc codebook in Phase 2 of 6 levels.

Figure 4.4. Comparison between the ideal and measured performances of the algorithm in both scenarios. The squares mark the maximum measured error of the algorithm, and the rhombi the maximum error when the algorithm performs ideally.

Figure 4.4 shows the empirical CDF of the localization error for both scenarios. Furthermore, in order to give more insight to the performance of the algorithm, the CDF of the ideal performance of the algorithm is also presented for both scenarios. The localization error is defined as the distance between the actual location of the RX and the estimated one. With the ideal case, the correct beam is always selected from the Bfr codebook, meaning the one that corresponds to the direction that is closest to the direction of the RX in Phase 1. Similarly, in Phase 2 the focal area that is closest to the location of the RX is selected from the Bfc codebook. The localization error in the ideal case derives from the fact that the RX location can be anywhere within the narrowest beam of the Bfr codebook in Phase 1, and the smallest focal area of the Bfc codebook in Phase 2. The same holds in the measured case. However, in the measured case there are two additional reasons that can increase the localization errors. The first reason is that in Phase 1 the RX direction uncertainty is in the order of the beamwidth, and it becomes more pronounced with the codewords of the lower codebook levels. Therefore, as the estimated direction of the RX possibly has an offset, the focal areas formed in Phase 2 also have that offset, which translates to localization errors, especially with large TX-RX distances. The second reason is that there are instances where the RX location is estimated to be in the wrong focal area, which also increases the localization error. This occurs because the definition of the focal areas is based on the

analytical expressions (4.5), and (4.6), which are for $\theta_r = 0$, i.e. for RXs at the broadside of the TX. As shown in [DSA24], the focal areas begin to change with $\theta_r \neq 0$. This effect is weak for the small focal areas of the higher codebook levels but becomes more pronounced with the large focal areas of the lower levels. Therefore, any error that occurs there is carried over to the higher levels. Even though this increases the average localization error, it is still low.

Overall, as the localization errors in Phase 1 depend on the TX-RX distance, and the sensitivity of Phase 2 in the success of Phase 1, Phase 1 can be considered the decisive factor with respect to the suppression of localization errors. The empirical CDF stops at the maximum localization error that is estimated from the simulations. As a result, this CDF also shows the maximum localization error from all RX locations. In scenario 1, the maximum error is 9.2 cm, the 99.9% maximum error is 6.6 cm, and the average localization error is 1.97 cm, while in scenario 2, they are 53 cm, 20 cm, and 4.2 cm respectively. In the ideal case of scenario 1, the maximum error is 4 cm, the 99.9% maximum error is 3.9 cm, and the average localization error is 1.95 cm, while in scenario 2 they are 8.1 cm, 7.9 cm, and 4 cm, respectively. Note that the localization error in scenario 2 is double that in scenario 1, and the reason is that the maximum distance d_0 in scenario 2 is double that in scenario 1. Moreover, the same codebook level is reached in both scenarios, which in scenario 2 offers half the resolution of that in scenario 1. For scenario 2 to reach the same resolution as scenario 1, an additional Bfc codebook level must be used in scenario 2, as shown in Table 4.1.

Figure 4.5. Performance of the algorithm with perfect Phase 1.

As previously stated, one reason for the localization errors is the direction uncertainty in Phase 1. The impact of Phase 1 in the localization errors is shown in Figure 6.5, where the empirical CDF of the localization error is shown for both the measured case and the case with perfect Phase 1. Perfect Phase 1 means that the exact direction of the RX is used in Phase 1. By comparing the two

cases, the impact of Phase 1 in the localization errors can be identified. In Scenario 1, the CDFs of the two cases are identical, as the maximum distance is relatively short. However, in Scenario 2 the maximum distance is longer and there are differences in the two CDFs. The most significant difference is the significantly lower maximum localization error that perfect Phase 1 offers, which is ~29 cm. There are two reasons for this. The first reason is that the exact direction of the RX is used, which negates the errors from Phase 1. If the direction at which the focal areas are formed and the direction of the RX are not identical, there is a possibility that a different focal area than the one closest to the RX will offer more power to the RX and will be selected to serve the UE. This happens because the power outside the 3dB focal area, and along its minor radius is significantly reduced, while the power along the major radius decreases at a considerably slower rate, as shown in Figure 4.2. The second reason is the shorter maximum distance of scenario 1, which translates to a Bfc codebook with relatively small focal areas that are more resistant to changes when $\theta_r \neq 0$, than the focal areas of the Bfc in scenario 2.

Figure 6.6. Performance of the algorithm in Phase 2 at different beam-focusing codebook levels.

The corners in the CDFs indicate a change in behavior that happens at different localization errors that depend on the last beam-focusing codebook level used. In Figure 4.6, the CDF of the localization error is investigated for different Bfc codebook levels in scenario 2 when in Phase 1 the Bfr codebook is used to estimate the direction of the RX. It is observed that with higher codebook levels the corner moves to lower localization errors as the focal areas are smaller. Moreover, with levels 7 and 8 the corners are at a lower probability, and an additional corner appears. The reason is that with these codebook levels, the focal areas are quite small, and the resolution of Phase 1 is insufficient. Therefore, a higher Bfr codebook level is required. This is also the reason that level 7 of the codebook performs better than level 8 at localization error 4 cm.

4.3.1 Practical considerations & low complexity approach

The success of the algorithm for achieving the desired resolution depends on successfully estimating the direction of the RX in Phase 1 and, therefore, finding the focal area along that direction that is closest to the RX in Phase 2. However, as shown in Figure 4.7(a) the direction estimation in Phase 1, has an angular error in the order of the beam-width. In this example, the footprint is $w_x = w_y = w = 7$ cm and the 3dB beam-width is $\theta_{3dB} = \sqrt{2 \ln 2} \lambda / (\pi w) = 0.61^\circ$. In general, narrow beams mean that the direction of the RX can be estimated with higher accuracy, reducing the localization error in Phase 2. An intuitive way to form narrower beams and increase the resolution in Phase 1 is to increase the active elements, as shown in Figure 4.7(a) and (b), which in this case can be done by increasing the beam-footprint. In the example of Figure 7 $w = 25$ cm and the 3dB beam-width is 0.17° . However, the beam-width refers to the beam in the far-field, while the beam in Figure 4.7(b) is clearly evolving in its near-field (the Rayleigh length is $z_R = 98$ m).

As larger footprints increase the Rayleigh length and push the near-to-far field transition to longer distances, increasing the footprint beyond some point becomes impractical as in for the area of interest the beams evolve entirely in their near-field and, as a result, instead of becoming narrower with the larger footprint, they become wider. Furthermore, in the near-field, beam diffraction is weak, and the beams propagate with practically constant peak power, as shown in Figure 4.7(b). Therefore, the received power along the direction of the propagation, and even among the adjacent beams of the codebook, is almost the same, as shown in Figure 4.7(c) where the beams of the Bfr codebook become almost indistinguishable at the RX. As a result, it is difficult to differentiate two adjacent beams of the Bfr codebook, particularly at the higher codebook levels that require larger beam-footprints.

Figure 4.7. Impact of footprint size on Phase 1 beamforming. (a) Small ($w = 7$ cm), and (b) large footprint ($w = 25$ cm) on the TX. (c) Received power of four adjacent beams at 10 m from the TX with the Bfr and R-bfr codebooks. The beams are generated with the 9th level of both codebooks, with $w = 25.58$ cm for the Bfr codebook, and $w = 5.41$ cm (footprint for level 7 of the Bfr codebook) for the R-bfr codebook. The dashed lines mark the directions where two adjacent beams offer the same power at the RX.

A simple solution to this problem in Phase 1 is to keep the footprint of a lower codebook level in the higher levels of the codebook. In other words, to use the footprint of a lower codebook level with the directions of the codewords in the higher levels. This codebook is thereafter called robust beamforming (R-bfr) codebook, and as shown in Figure 4.7(c), it provides increased power with narrower beams than the Bfr codebook, making it more robust to AWGN.

In the simulations, the R-bfr codebook keeps the footprint of the 7th codebook level in the higher levels. As a result, the footprint radius is 6.5 cm, and the Rayleigh length ~6.6 m. As an example, Figure 4.8(a) shows the probability of success for the two scenarios as a function of the average AWGN power at the RX, P_n . The algorithm is considered successful when the localization error is at most equal to the resolution presented in Table 4.1. In both scenarios, the R-bfr codebook is shown to be significantly more robust to AWGN than the Bfr codebook. For example, the probability of success with the Bfr codebook starts decreasing from $P_n = -80$ dBm, while with the R-bfr codebook from $P_n = -40$ dBm. Furthermore, the probability of success reaches 0 at 20 dBm in both scenarios and with both codebooks. Moreover, in both scenarios, the difference between the two codebooks increases in the range from $P_n = -80$ dBm to -40 dBm where the difference is the highest at 40%, and then it starts decreasing. Figure 4.8(b) shows the average localization error, as a function of P_n . The minimum and maximum values of the average localization error are the same with both codebooks in each scenario. Specifically, respect the minimum value in scenario 1 is 2 cm, and the maximum is 2.1 m, while in scenario 2, they are 4.2 cm, and 3.4 m. Regardless of the scenario, the average localization error with the Bfr codebook, is the same from -110 dBm to -90 dBm. With the R-bfr codebook, the algorithm can retain low average localization error even with higher values, as in both scenarios, the average error is the same from -110 to -50 dBm (see inset in Figure 4.8(b)). The maximum value for the average error is again reached at 20 dBm.

Figure 4.8. (a) Probability of success for the two scenarios and codebooks, and (b) average localization error vs average AWGN power. For convenience, the inset shows the probability of success for average AWGN power up to -50 dBm.

Figure 4.9 shows the empirical CDF of the localization error for both scenarios, with and without AWGN at the RX, and with both the Bfr and R-bfr codebooks. The performance in scenarios 1, and 2 are shown in (a), and (b), respectively. In the case with $P_n = -50$ dBm, the difference in probability of success between the two codebooks is ~32% in both scenarios as shown in Figure 4.8(a). As previously stated, with the Bfr codebook, the algorithm is prone to errors due to the presence of AWGN. For example, in scenario 1 in Figure 4.9(a), in the case without AWGN, the overall maximum error with the Bfr codebook is 9.2 cm, while in the case with $P_n = -50$ dBm it is 1.29 m. Furthermore, the 99.9% maximum error without AWGN, and with $P_n = -50$ dBm is 6.6 cm and 91 cm, while the average localization error is 2 cm, and 7 cm. With the R-bfr codebook, the maximum error is 9.2 cm in the case without AWGN, and with $P_n = -50$ dBm it is 16.5 cm. Moreover, the 99.9% maximum error is 6.6 cm, and the average localization error is 2 cm in all cases. It is observed that with the Bfr codebook, both the overall and the 99.9% maximum errors increase significantly in the presence of AWGN. On the other hand, w. With the R-bfr codebook, they are almost the same with the case without AWGN. In scenario 2 in (b), the effect of AWGN is more pronounced due to the larger size and the lower power density of the focal areas which is the result of the increased d_0 . In the case without AWGN with the Bfr codebook, the maximum error is 53 cm, the 99.9% maximum error is 20 cm, and the average localization error is 4.3 cm, while in the case with $P_n = -50$ dBm, they have increased to 2.8 m, 1.3 m, and 14 cm. On the other hand, with the R-bfr codebook the maximum error is 53 cm, the 99.9% maximum error is 21 cm, and the average localization error is 4.2 cm for the cases without AWGN, while with $P_n = -50$ dBm, they are 2.2 m, 24 cm, and 4.3 cm.

Figure 4.9. Empirical CDF of the localization error in scenarios 1, and 2, in (a), and (b), respectively. The comparison is

between the Bfr and R-bfr codebooks, with and without AWGN. The squares mark the maximum measured error of the algorithm with the Bfr codebook, and the rhombi the maximum measured error with the R-bfr codebook. For convenience, the insets show a small part of the CDFs.

4.4 Mobile User Tracking

Previously, the localization process was described in a manner of exhaustive search with the binary tree search method. However, this method is unsuitable for tracking the location of mobile users, where it must be performed fast and frequently. In order to adjust the localization algorithm to the mobile user scenario, the aforementioned algorithm takes the role of the initialization process which is performed in the first three timeslots. Next, the algorithm starts predicting the location of the user in the next timeslot, assuming linear motion with constant speed by using the estimations in the previous three timeslots. Then, the TX scans a small area around the predicted location with fewer codewords from a few of the highest codebook levels in both phases. To scan a small area, the TX utilizes only a few codebook levels in each phase, therefore reducing the angular and radial range to search.

4.4.1 Linear user motions

In this subsection, the user motion is a randomly generated linear motion in the areas of interest of the two scenarios. The first and last locations of the motions are randomly generated with the uniform distribution in angle and range. Moreover, the minimum distance that the user covers is 3 m, and the minimum distance of the RX from the surface where the TX is placed, is 10 cm. In scenario 1, the Bfr codebook has $L_t = 10$ levels, and the Bfc codebook has $L_r = 6$ levels, while in scenario 2, they have $L_t = 11$, and $L_r = 7$ levels, respectively. After the initialization ends, in Phase 1, the algorithm starts from the $(L_t - 3)$ -th codebook level, and the TX scans four directions around the predicted location, while in Phase 2, the algorithm only utilizes the highest codebook level and the TX scans four focal areas. Therefore, the overhead is significantly lower in comparison to the localization of static users that was previously presented. Moreover, since the areas of interest are known to the TX, the predicted locations that fall outside of them are adjusted angle-wise to be inside of them. For example, if the location predicted results in an angle of 27° , while the maximum angle in the area of interest is 25° , the algorithm uses the beams that are close to 25° to scan the area.

Figure 4.10. Empirical CDF of the localization error from location tracking of mobile users in scenarios 1, and 2. The markers show the maximum error in each scenario.

In Figure 4.10, the empirical CDF is presented for the two scenarios but with mobile users. The performance of the tracking algorithm is almost the same in the two scenarios. Specifically, the maximum error in scenario 1 is 25.6 cm, which is slightly lower than in scenario 2, where it is 26.5 cm. In contrast, in the case with static users, the maximum error in scenario 1 is 9.2 cm, while in scenario 2 it is 53 cm. Moreover, the 99.9% maximum error is 3.9 cm, while the average error is 2 cm regardless of the scenario, which are almost the same as the ideal case of scenario 1. The reason for the low errors is that the algorithm utilizes only the last codebook level in Phase 2 that generates the smallest focal areas which are mostly unaffected when $\theta_r \neq 0$.

4.4.2 Random user motions

The random motion is generated with the random walk process, with three points, the first of which is generated randomly with the uniform distribution on the xz plane. The distance between the first and the second point, is the same as the distance between the second and the third point, which is 3 m. Then, the points are connected with interpolation as shown in Figure 4.11, to form the trajectory, which is discretized according to the number of timeslots when the tracking estimation takes place. With few timeslots, the trajectory can appear to be random, which reduces the prediction accuracy and can lead to the algorithm failing to estimate the correct direction, and therefore, the user's location. With more timeslots, the discretized trajectory starts resembling the actual trajectory, and therefore, the accuracy of the prediction increases, which then increases the performance of the algorithm. Moreover, the users move randomly in the area of interest of scenario 2. Unless otherwise stated, after the initialization, in Phase 1 the algorithm uses the 5 highest codebook levels, while in Phase 2 only the highest codebook level.

Furthermore, in the starting codebook level of both phases the algorithm uses four codewords. As previously stated, by using only the highest codebook level in Phase 2, the localization errors that appear when $\theta_r \neq 0$, disappear.

Figure 4.11. Example of random motions. The straight lines show the trajectories, and the markers show the samples that are taken at specific timeslots.

In Figure 4.12, the probability of success is presented in (a), and the average localization error in (b), as a function of the number of timeslots where the mobile user localization is performed, for different codebook (cb) sizes. In (a), it is observed that increasing the number of timeslots increases the probability of success. Specifically, with a large codebook it becomes harder to accurately estimate the TX-RX distance as after the initialization only the highest cb level is used in Phase 2. This changes, however, by increasing the number of timeslots. For example, with 3 cb levels, the probability of success at 20, 40, and 60 timeslots, is 92.9%, 99.7%, and 99.9%, with 6 cb levels it is 76.9%, 99.7%, and 99.95%, and with 7 cb levels, it is 57.2%, 95.8%, and 99.65%. In (b), large codebooks, and therefore, small focal areas in Phase 2 translate to a lower average localization error. For example, with 20, 40 and 60 timeslots, the average localization error with 3 cb levels is 38 cm, 31.6 cm and 31.5 cm, while with 7 cb levels it decreases from 50 cm to 2.3 cm, and 2 cm. For reference, the major radii, marked with dashed lines, are 75 cm with 3 cb levels, and 4.6 cm with 7 cb levels.

Figure 4.12. (a) Probability of success of localization, and (b) average localization error for different number of timeslots and codebook levels in Phase 2 for the same motions as in (a). The inset in (a) focuses on a small part of the plot to better show the difference between the codebook sizes, and the dashed lines in (b) show the major radii of the focal areas with the last codebook level.

Figure 4.13 presents the empirical CDF of the localization error with 11 cb levels in Phase 1, and 7 cb levels in Phase 2, for 40, 50, and 60 timeslots. It is observed that with more timeslots the localization errors are significantly reduced as the prediction becomes more accurate. For example, with 40 timeslots, 99% of all localization errors are lower than 12.7 cm, with 50 timeslots lower than 5 cm, and with 60 timeslots lower than 3.9 cm, and the maximum localization error is 59.4 m, 18, and 17.4 cm, respectively. This shows that increasing the number of timeslots after a certain number of timeslots yields diminishing returns.

Figure 4.13. Empirical CDF of the localization error for different number of timeslots for the case with 7 cb levels. The markers show the maximum error in each case.

Figure 4.14 shows the probability of success in (a), and the average localization error in (b), as a function of the number of timeslots, for different codebook sizes in Phase 1. It is observed that with codebooks of 9-10 cb levels the probability of success in (a) is at most 30%, and 76.4% respectively, as the narrowest generated beams with these codebooks are relatively wide in relation to the focal areas. With larger codebooks (e.g. 11-12 cb levels) that generate narrower beams, the probability of success increases to 99.6%. It is evident that with few timeslots, the codebook with 12 cb levels offers worse performance than the one with 11 cb levels. The reason for this is that the same number of codewords is used to scan the area regardless of the codebook size, which means that with higher codebook levels the beams are narrower, and a smaller area is scanned. By increasing the number of timeslots, the two codebooks offer the same probability of success as the prediction becomes more accurate. This is also shown in (b) with the average localization error. For example, the average localization error with 12 cb levels starts from 61 cm with 20 timeslots, decreases to 13 cm with 30 timeslots, and is less than 2.5 cm starting with 40 timeslots.

Figure 4.14. (a) Probability of success of localization, and (b) average localization error for different number of timeslots and codebook levels in Phase 1 for the same motions as in (a)

4.5 Conclusions

A localization algorithm was presented that can be implemented with both LAAs and LISs, and offers low average localization error, which, depending on the maximum distance from the TX in the area of interest, is in the order of 2–4 cm. The localization algorithm consists of hierarchical beam-training and a hierarchical ranging algorithm that was presented here and is the equivalent of the hierarchical beam-training method. Moreover, a simple approach was presented to make the beamforming codebook more robust to AWGN. The performance of the proposed algorithm was presented through the probability of success, average localization error, and empirical CDFs. It was shown that the performance of the algorithm depends on the resolution of Phase 1 plays a decisive role in the accuracy of the localization algorithm. A location tracking algorithm was also presented and evaluated with two kinds of motions, linear and random. The evaluation was demonstrated with the probability of success, the average localization error, and the empirical CDF of the localization error. In the case with linear motions, the algorithm offers higher overall accuracy in scenarios with long distances from the TX and lower overhead than the localization for static users. In the random motion case, it was observed that with enough timeslots, the algorithm can achieve 99.6% probability of success, an average localization error of 2 cm, and 99% of the localization errors are below 4 cm.

4.6 References

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5 AI-based Optimization of 5GNSS for Robust 5G-NR and GNSS Localization

The 5GNSS framework [CB24] represents a novel approach to integrating Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS) with 5G New Radio (5G-NR) to enhance localization accuracy and reliability. Its architecture is designed to leverage the complementary strengths of GNSS and 5G-NR while addressing the limitations of standalone systems. This section provides an overview of the 5GNSS architecture and highlights potential areas where machine learning (ML) techniques can optimize system performance, supported by insights from baseline evaluations.

5GNSS optimization aligns directly with the broader objective of developing smart schemes for resource allocation, control, and coordination of multiple sensors. By leveraging ML techniques for anchor selection, adaptive data fusion, and error correction, we enhance the reliability and accuracy of multi-sensor localization, a key challenge in dynamic wireless environments. The ML-driven optimization of GNSS and 5G-NR fusion provides an example of intelligent network control. Furthermore, our ML-based anomaly detection mechanisms, which focused on identifying synchronization errors, bias estimation, and suboptimal anchor configurations, contribute to the broader vision of data-driven and adaptive network management. These advances also complement coverage optimization and improve localization accuracy. By integrating our work into the broader framework of AI-driven resource management, we contribute to the development of next-generation localization systems through the communicate-to-sense INSTINCT approach. This ensures optimal operation even in challenging environments and scenarios, such as urban canyons and emergency situations.

The architecture of the 5GNSS system is depicted in Figure 5.1 and composed of several interconnected components that facilitate the fusion of GNSS and 5G-NR data for accurate and robust positioning. This modular design allows 5GNSS to adapt to varying environmental conditions, making it suitable for diverse scenarios, including urban canyons and suburban areas.

- 1. GNSS and 5G-NR Measurements:** This layer collects raw data from GNSS satellites and 5G-NR gNodeBs (gNBs). GNSS provides satellite ephemeris and pseudo-ranges, while 5G-NR relies on Time of Flight (ToF) measurements obtained from uplink Sounding Reference Signals (SRS).
- 2. Synchronization Management:** Synchronization between GNSS and 5G-NR systems is managed using GNSS clocks as a reference for the network. An iterative estimation corrects synchronization biases, ensuring consistent time references for both systems.
- 3. Rate Matching and Stacking:** To facilitate data fusion, GNSS and 5G-NR measurements are rate-matched and stacked into unified vectors. This process ensures temporal and spatial alignment of both systems.

4. **Weighted Non-linear Least Squares (WNLS) Estimator:** The WNLS estimator performs multilateration to compute the user equipment (UE) position. This involves correcting clock offsets, inter-system biases, and synchronization errors while weighting GNSS and 5G-NR contributions based on signal quality.

Figure 5.1: Potential for ML optimization over the 5GNSS framework

Baseline evaluations underscore the advantages of the 5GNSS system:

- **Coverage Improvements:** The system achieves better coverage with fewer anchors compared to standalone GNSS or 5G-NR systems. Coverage maps indicate significant gains in challenging environments, such as urban canyons.
- **Accuracy Gains:** Experimental results demonstrate up to a 46% improvement in urban canyons and up to a 93% improvement in suburban areas over standalone systems. These gains highlight the potential for further optimization through ML techniques.

While the 5GNSS framework demonstrates performance improvements over standalone systems, there are specific areas where ML techniques can further enhance its capabilities:

1. **Anchor Selection for Coverage Optimization:**

Anchor selection involves choosing the most suitable GNSS satellites and 5G-NR gNBs for localization. Currently, algorithmic methods are used for distinguishing Line of Sight (LoS) from Non-Line of Sight (NLoS) conditions. The intuition behind the improvements due to the optimal anchor selection are exemplified in Figure 5.2, depicting the coverage enhancements due to the ability to utilize localization anchors of both technologies.

ML is expected to further improve and optimize anchor selection by:

- Predicting the quality of GNSS and 5G-NR signals based on environmental factors (e.g., urban clutter, weather conditions).

- Learning optimal anchor configurations for different scenarios, maximizing coverage and minimizing errors.

Baseline results indicate that increasing gNB density improves 5GNSS performance compared to GNSS-only systems. ML-based anchor selection could refine this process by identifying optimal configurations for specific environments.

Figure 5.2: System availability comparison, stand-alone GNSS vs stand-alone 5G-NR vs 5GNSS

2. Weighting Mechanisms for Data Fusion:

The fusion of GNSS and 5G-NR data currently relies on static or heuristic weighting schemes. ML can enhance this by:

- Dynamically adjusting weights based on signal quality, synchronization errors, and Dilution of Precision (DOP).
- Mitigating residual errors by learning patterns across datasets and prioritizing high-quality measurements.

Experimental data shows that 5GNSS significantly reduces positioning errors in urban canyons compared to standalone systems. ML-based weighting mechanisms could further minimize these errors, especially under challenging conditions.

3. Error Correction and Bias Estimation:

Synchronization errors and clock biases are currently addressed through iterative estimation. Accuracy enhancements of the fusion of 5G-NR and 5GNSS under the presence of synchronization errors are exemplified in Figure 5.3.

ML could:

- Predict and correct synchronization errors using historical and real-time data.
- Enhance clock offset estimation by identifying recurring biases in GNSS and 5G-NR.

Figure 5.3: Comparison of the robustness to synchronization error between stand-alone 5G-NR and 5GNSS

5GNSS provides a robust foundation for integrating GNSS and 5G-NR systems, addressing key localization challenges. By incorporating ML-based optimization, the framework can dynamically adapt to environmental conditions, improve anchor selection, enhance data fusion, correct residual errors, and amplify the overall accuracy and robustness of the 5GNSS framework, unlocking its full potential for next-generation localization systems.

5.1 References

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6 Deep Learning for Realistic Coverage Map

Predictions

Understanding and modeling radio propagation is key for designing, planning and optimizing future wireless networks [KSN18, AMZ17] and enable modern network applications such as autonomous driving, drone-based delivery, and extended reality (XR). These emerging applications require low-latency and highly reliable wireless communication, making accurate signal modeling even more critical. As a result, efficient network performance analysis is essential to ensure high quality of experience (QoE) for users and devices.

Signal strength maps (SSMs) [EAC19, JBC20] provide a structured way to represent the received signal strength across a geographical area, offering valuable insights into network coverage, interference, and overall performance. SSMs can be generated through ray-tracing based simulations or costly drive tests. On the one hand, simulations are widely used but they are computationally expensive, and they do not fully capture real-world complexities, such as building material properties or moving objects. In addition, the computational cost increases with the number of ray-object interactions, increasing the computational time for large geographical areas.

On the other hand, drive tests consist of equipping a vehicle with specialized equipment and driving through a pre-defined route collecting data on signal strength and other metrics. This method provides highly accurate real-world measurements of the signal across a geographical area. However, it has the limitation of being labor-intensive, time-consuming, and expensive to conduct. In addition, they are limited to specific geographic areas, leading to incomplete coverage data.

In this work, we explore the use of Deep Learning (DL) tools to build a cost-efficient and lightweight model for SSM estimation. To do that, we represent the real-world environment as a graph and employ Graph Neural Networks (GNNs) [JPM24] to effectively model the intricate interactions between transmitted signals and the physical surroundings. Our approach provides a fast, accurate data-driven solution for coverage maps estimation, offering network operators a powerful tool to enhance mobile coverage maps.

6.1 Problem Definition

To model radio signal propagation in urban environments, we convert the real-world environments into structured 3D digital representations, referred to as scenes. Each scene encodes essential environmental information such as building geometry, location and orientation. We also include in the scene the transmitter antenna location and configuration. The 3D building data is obtained from OpenStreetMap [HW28] while the transmitter configurations are extracted from a dataset of real-world antenna deployments from a mobile network operator.

For each scene, a set of points, called receiver points R , is placed uniformly at a height of 1.5 meters, simulating mobile device placements at pedestrian level.

The objective is to predict the received signal strength (RSS) for all receivers $r \in R$. For each receiver, a graph G is built (See Section 6.2.2. Graph Representation). Then, our GNN-based model processes this graph and outputs a value that represents the RSS for the given receiver. The task is to learn a function:

$$\hat{y}_r = f(G; \theta),$$

where G is the graph representation of the 3D scene, θ represents the learnable parameters of the GNN-based model, and y_r is the predicted RSS value at receiver r .

6.2 System Architecture

6.2.1 Data Generation

As previously mentioned, using DL to model signal propagation in 3D real-world environments allows to reduce the computational complexity of utilizing traditional methods to estimate coverage maps (e.g., simulations). However, datasets have a fundamental role not only for training and validation of the proposed algorithms but also to guarantee the trustworthiness of the proposed solution.

For this reason, in line with the GNN-based model for estimating coverage, and as part of the WP3 activities of INSTINCT, a database of geographical scenes is being generated. A brief description of the procedure and tools utilized in the dataset generation is presented in this subsection.

Our objective is to create a comprehensive dataset of scenes to be used in SIONNA RT [JAS23]. One of the traditional approaches to create a scene is combining OpenStreetMap (OSM) and Blender tool [BLE19]. The basic procedure to create one scene is to utilize blender application with OSM and Mitsuba add-on [MDT19]. OSM allows to download the geographical data in a specific region while the Mitsuba add-on allows to save the scene in a format suitable for SIONNA. This procedure is valid for manually creating a few scenes. However, as the objective is to create a dataset with multiple scenes, an automatization algorithm is being implemented.

To briefly describe this automatization process, OSM and Blender APIs are being combined to obtain the complete scenes surrounding deployment of antennas in the real-world. Square scenes (e.g., 150x150, 200x200 square meter) are being considered, in which a base station with multiple sectors is allocated in the center of the scene. Once the scenes are created, it is envisioned to compute the coverage maps for each sector in the scenes, using the 3D ray tracing tool of SIONNA. The result of this process is a dataset of detailed coverage maps (one per sector), which serves as the ground truth in the training process of any AI-based SSM estimator.

Figure 6.1 illustrates a simulated scene with a real antenna placement and orientation, the buildings and the RSS map. In our work, the information contained in the scene is processed by our GNN-based model to predict the RSS map. These maps offer insights into signal propagation

and coverage, making them an essential resource for developing and testing AI algorithms in telecommunications and related fields.

Figure 6.1: Image of a 3D scene downloaded from OSM and simulated in SIONNA. The blue point corresponds to the real-world antenna placement and configuration where the black arrow indicates the orientation.

6.2.2 Graph Representation

Once the scenes have been downloaded and the dataset has been created, we proceed to convert them to a point cloud representation. This means that instead of representing the 3D geometry of each building using 2D planes, we leverage a point cloud that captures the geometrical information of the buildings. In addition to the geometric information, each scene includes a transmitter and multiple receivers. The transmitter is placed according to the relative positions in the real-world environment and the receivers are uniformly distributed across the scene in a 2D plane at a height of 1.5 meters. Once all the elements of the scene have been placed, they are converted to a point cloud, where each point is converted to a node of the graph. Each node and edge have a feature vector with features associated to the orientation of the nodes, distances between nodes and the angles between edges and node orientations. We build a graph for each receiver, changing the connectivity of the graph accordingly. Then, each graph is processed by our GNN model, outputting the predicted RSS value for the corresponding receiver. This procedure is repeated for all receiver points from the point cloud representation.

6.2.3 Model

Once we complete the graph representation, we use Message Passing Neural Networks (MPNNs) [JSF17] to implement our GNN-based model. This neural architecture processes all the graph-structured information and exploits the relationships between the different nodes in the graph. MPNNs are deep learning models specifically tailored to process graph-structured information. For example, unlike other popular neural network models (e.g., convolutional, recurrent, multi-layer perceptron), these models support graphs of variable number of nodes and edges and, more importantly, they are equivariant to node and edge permutations [JPM24]. In the context of coverage prediction, this means that by representing the 3D scene as a graph, MPNN-based models can find symmetries or equivalent patterns (e.g., combinations of relative distances and

orientations) between the scenes seen during training and new ones where the model is applied after training.

6.3 Performance Evaluation

In this set of experiments, we train our GNN-based model and evaluate its performance on one real-world 3D scene of 150x150 meters from Cambridge, in the United Kingdom. We select a deployed antenna, we download the building information from OSM, and we construct a dataset by simulating different antenna placements within this scene. For each placement, we generate an RSS map using SIONNA.

The training set consists of 10 randomly selected antenna placements, while the test set includes 4 distinct placements that are not used during training. Across all experiments, the antenna's orientation and configuration (i.e., tilt, azimuth, and height) remain fixed, and we only vary its latitude and longitude position.

Each sample in our dataset is represented as a graph connecting building nodes, the antenna node, and one single receiver node within the scene. Node and edge features are scaled by dividing by their maximum value to ensure numerical stability. From each generated coverage map and from a total of 8064 receiver placements, we allocate 70% of the placements for training and 30% for testing. The model is implemented using TensorFlow 2.18 [MAP15]. We predict the RSS values for all coverage points, which can be located indoors or outdoors. The model is expected to learn the influence of the environment on signal propagation, including the impact of obstacles such as buildings.

During training and testing, we compute the Mean Squared Error (MSE), Mean Absolute Error (MAE), and Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) with respect to the ground truth obtained from SIONNA simulations. The final model selection is based on the lowest MAE achieved on the test set. After training, we assess the model's generalization by evaluating its performance on 4 unseen antenna placements.

Figure 6.2: Evaluation results of the GNN-based model for predicting the RSS on the antenna position $-22.86, -40$.

Figure 6.2 presents the difference between the predicted and ground truth RSS maps for one of the 4 different antenna placements from the test set. Specifically, the antenna was placed at $(-22.86, -40.0)$ meters relative to the original position (i.e., the star indicates the antenna placement). Warmer colors (red) indicate regions where the model underestimates the signal, while cooler colors (blue) represent overestimation (note that the original dBm is a negative value). The white parts of the map indicate that the model's prediction is very close to the ground truth. On average, the mean absolute error of all the predictions in this scene is 3.22 dBm.

Figure 6.3: Ground truth RSS map on the antenna position $-22.86, -40$.

These results suggest that the model effectively generalizes to new antenna placements, with moderate variation in error across different locations. The variation in accuracy may be attributed to differences in environmental obstructions, such as buildings affecting signal propagation, or challenging indoor coverage conditions.

In Figure 6.3 we observe the ground truth values for the same experiment. The darker regions indicate no coverage, and this is because the samples fall within a building (i.e., indoor samples). From these results, we can observe that the highest errors tend to appear in areas behind buildings, where signal propagation is naturally more complex due to obstructions. This suggests that while the model captures the overall coverage patterns, it struggles in regions with significant shadowing effects, likely due to limited training data or insufficient generalization to extreme cases of blockage.

6.4 Conclusions

In our work we aim at building a GNN-based model for predicting the RSS across a real-world scene. We proposed representing the 3D environmental information using a point cloud, where the points are then converted to nodes connected to build a graph. Each node and edge from this graph have some features associated that are relevant to predict the RSS. Once trained, our method is fast to execute, and the experimental results show that it can accurately predict the RSS on a scene with a different antenna placement not seen during training, achieving a MAE of 3.22 dBm. These results indicate that the combination of the point cloud data representation and

the GNN-based model is promising in modeling the signal propagation in a 3D environment. As next step, we are planning to evaluate further our methodology and make more complex and realistic experiments.

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7 Beam-Space Intermodulation Suppression for LoS MIMO System with Nonlinear Power Amplifiers

The next generation of wireless communication systems is characterized by the deployment of massive multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) technology, which leverages a large number of antennas to transmit and receive signals [MLH20], [LWP24]. As a key enabler of advanced wireless systems, massive MIMO promises substantial improvements in spectral efficiency due to its ability to focus energy precisely towards intended users, which is especially important in dense network environments [DH23]. The inherent spatial multiplexing capability of massive MIMO facilitates simultaneous transmission to multiple users, leading to significant gains in throughput and system capacity [ZZD24].

However, despite these advantages, the practical realization of massive MIMO faces several challenges, particularly related to hardware constraints [LLXL20]. A traditional massive MIMO system requires a dedicated radio-frequency (RF) chain for each antenna element to process the signals. These RF chains, comprising power amplifiers (PAs) and up-converters, are critical for amplification and conversion from baseband to RF signals [WZD23]. The power amplifiers are usually costly and have high energy consumption, and more importantly, they are nonlinear [AJE19], [LRP22]. Moreover, a high-efficiency PA is achieved when it is operated close to the saturation region [YRG19]. This issue hinders the practical realization of massive MIMO from achieving higher performance [LP24], [LWP23].

Fig. 7.1: System-level illustration for power leakage issue: user-A and user-B are served by different mobile network operators.

In line-of-sight (LoS) propagation scenarios, the effects of PA distortion are particularly pronounced in massive MIMO systems [ABV19]. The distortion generated from each PA is strongly correlated and combined coherently in the space, which degrades the performance significantly.

Moreover, the distortion is beamformed not only in the direction of the intended user but also towards unintended, spurious directions due to intermodulation (IM) distortion [LVP18]. This results in the creation of intermodulation beams (IM beams), which, depending on their intensity and direction, can interfere with other users or even disrupt adjacent systems operating [MGE18]. The LoS channel represents a worst-case scenario for power leakage, as the PA distortion combines coherently in these settings, leading to more severe interference [GSR17]. Empirical measurements using a massive MIMO testbed under indoor LoS conditions have demonstrated that nonlinear distortions can arise and coherently combine in space [LYK21]. The phenomenon of IM beam interference is especially problematic in densely deployed networks. For instance, Fig. 7.1 illustrates a situation where an edge user of base station B experiences significant interference from IM beams generated by base station A. In this case, the IM beams' power level becomes comparable to that of the desired signal from base station B, causing severe performance degradation due to interference. Given the critical impact of PA nonlinearity, a variety of techniques have been devoted to enabling PAs to operate near their saturation point while maintaining acceptable link quality.

7.1 Contributions

In this work, we focus on the nonlinear distortion in a massive MIMO system with nonlinear power amplifiers. It is known that the distortion generated by nonlinear power amplifiers is beamformed in the ILoS channel. Spurious emissions are caused by beamformed IM distortion and form as IM beams. We propose a precoder for IM beam suppression in the MIMO system, which aims to suppress the intermodulation beams while maintaining beamforming for the intended receivers. First, we derive the direction of the IM beams under the free-space LoS channel condition. Then, the intermodulation suppression (IMS) precoder is proposed by maximizing the signal-to-leakage ratio. Moreover, we propose a generalized IMS precoder to achieve the trade-off between the intended signal coherent combination and IM beam suppression. Adjusting the weights of the precoder can suppress the IM beams while ensuring a coherent combination of signals at intended receivers. Simulation results show that the proposed IMS precoder can suppress the IM beams and reduce the power leakage in spurious directions. The power gain obtained by the proposed IMS precoder can approach to the maximum ratio transmission while achieving substantial suppression gain for the IM beams.

7.2 Performance Evaluation

In this section, we evaluate the proposed IMS precoder through numerical simulations. We consider a 3rd-order quasi-memoryless polynomial model to describe the behavior of power amplifiers (PAs). The signal waveform used is a 20 MHz LTE OFDM waveform sampled at 120 MHz, and a Kaiser window is applied for spectral containment [ABV19].

We simulate a MIMO transmitter with $M = 100$ antennas and PAs, serving two users ($\theta_1 = -60^\circ$ and $\theta_2 = 60^\circ$) in the same frequency band under free-space line-of-sight (LoS) propagation. For simplicity, the channel coefficient $\alpha_k = 1$ for all $\theta_k \in [-90^\circ, 90^\circ]$ in (1). The suppression factors are

set as $c_1 = c_2 = 1$ and $c_{IM,n} = 3$. We also consider $L = 10$ suppression directions in the undesired direction window. The angular suppression range is $\Delta = 2^\circ$ with a spacing of 0.2° . The out-of-band (OOB) region is defined as $[-3B/2, -B/2]$ and $[B/2, 3B/2]$ to characterize the IM beam power leakage.

First, we present the in-band and OOB IM beam patterns for two users ($\theta_1 = -60^\circ$ and $\theta_2 = 60^\circ$) under the MRT precoder and the proposed IMS precoder. In Fig. 1.(a), we show the beam patterns with the MRT precoder. Like the generalized IMS precoder with $\eta = 0$, the MRT precoder ensures the maximum coherent combination of the intended signal but does not account for intermodulation beams. As seen in Fig. 8.2(a), the nonlinear PAs generate intermodulation beams both in-band and out-of-band.

In Fig. 7.2(b), we show the beam patterns under the IMS precoder when $\eta = 0.6$. Compared to Fig. 7.2(a), the intermodulation beams are clearly suppressed, while the coherent combination of signals in the desired user directions is maintained. This demonstrates that the proposed IMS

Fig. 7.2: Spatial beam pattern with different precoders: antenna number $M=100$.

precoder effectively suppresses intermodulation beams while ensuring coherent beamforming for the intended users.

In Fig. 7.2(c), we increase the weight η on the non-coherent part and present the beam pattern with the IMS precoder when $\eta = 0.8$. As η increases, more antennas are dedicated to suppressing signal leakage in undesired directions, leading to further suppression of intermodulation beams.

7.3 Conclusions

In this section, we focus on the spurious emission of distortion in a MIMO system with nonlinear power amplifiers. It is shown that the distortion generated by nonlinear power amplifiers is beamformed in the LoS channel. We propose a precoder for IM beams suppression in the MIMO system, which aims at suppressing the intermodulation beams while maintaining beamforming for the intended receivers. By deriving the direction of the IM beams under the LoS channel model, we proposed a beam-space precoder to maximize the signal-to-leakage ratio. Moreover, a generalized IMS precoder is proposed to achieve the trade-off between the coherent combination of the intended signal and suppression of IM beams. Adjusting the weights of the precoder can suppress the IM beams while ensuring a coherent combination of signals at intended receivers. Simulation results show that the proposed IMS precoder can obtain approximately the same in-band gain as MRT while achieving a substantial suppression gain for the IM beams.

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8 AI-based Optimization for DoA Estimation and Task Offloading in RIS-aided ISAC Systems

The advent of integrated sensing and communication (ISAC) systems marks a transformative era in military surveillance, essential for modern warfare [AMP23]. The integration of ground, aerial, and space networks in sixth-generation (6G) communication systems is a game-changer that delivers unmatched levels of global connectivity, low-latency communication, accurate sensing capabilities, and distributed task offloading [LTD24], [GA22], [HAL23]. These capabilities are instrumental in time-sensitive surveillance systems, making them an essential component for the next level of military operations.

ISAC systems are essential in achieving a dual-purpose goal: real-time environmental sensing for threat detection and dynamic communication for, e.g., command and control [LLL22]. The authors of [LLL22] proposed an ISAC system aided by reconfigurable intelligent surfaces (RISs) to maximize communication and sensing performance metrics while maintaining robust communication links. Pan et al. investigated the use of unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) to provide ISAC services [PAL23]. They take advantage of UAV mobility to improve accuracy in target location estimation and ensure quality of-service (QoS) in communication [PAL23], [LDY20]. Further study revealed that a UAV-mounted RIS is capable of providing reliable coverage for ISAC systems [LLL23], [MKW24].

The direction-of-arrival (DoA) estimation is crucial in the sensing component of ISAC systems, particularly if we consider surveillance applications [PAL23], [EMS23]. It involves determining the angle at which a received signal arrives, which is crucial for accurately localizing and tracking unauthorized flying objects (UFOs) or potential threats. In their research, Chen et al. [CCG24] investigated the use of passive beamforming with RIS for estimating the DoA of ground vehicles. Multiple measurements were analyzed to determine the ISAC system's theoretical Cramer-Rao lower bound (CRLB) in estimating the DoA [PAL23], [CCG24], [WFH22].

To optimize systems with limited resources for sensing, communication, and computation, implementing a robust resource allocation strategy within the ISAC framework is crucial. The evolution of artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML), followed by advancements in deep learning (DL), significantly overcomes the hurdles of traditional optimization techniques [WW23], [LZL23]. AI and ML algorithms introduce unprecedented adaptability, learning capability, and predictive analysis, enabling sophisticated and efficient resource allocation strategies that were previously unattainable [GWF23], [LZL22]. Wang and Wong demonstrated that DL methods applied to ISAC-enabled predictive beamforming outperform traditional methods by bypassing intermediate state parameter estimation [WW23]. The authors of [LZL23] used advanced deep reinforcement learning (DRL) algorithms in securing ISAC systems, balancing communication efficacy with security against eavesdropping threats. DRL algorithms excel in sequential decision-making environments, making them ideal for dynamic, uncertain systems through continuous interaction with the environment [LZL23], [GWF23], [LZL22]. Using

a DRL-based deep deterministic policy gradient (DDPG) algorithm, Gong et al. solved the joint optimization problem of vehicular task scheduling and resource allocation in an ISAC framework [GWF23]. In another work, Liu et al. explored a DRL-based proximal policy optimization (PPO) algorithm in a multi-user multiple-input single-output (MISO) scenario to maximize system capacity in an RIS-aided ISAC system [LZL22].

8.1 Contributions

Against this background, we provide the following main contributions::

- **Optimized ISAC System Balance:** The proposed framework achieves an optimal balance between sensing for DoA estimation and communication for task offloading. Employing UAV-mounted RISs enables simultaneous DoA estimation and sensing of UFOs. The framework's novel integration of root mean squared error (RMSE), CRLB, and semidefinite programming (SDP) establishes a statistically robust foundation for DoA estimation, enhancing accuracy and reducing potential errors within a quantum-DRL environment.
- **Sophisticated Task Offloading Scheme:** By utilizing non-terrestrial networks, including satellites and aerial platforms, the proposed scheme addresses terrestrial network limitations and facilitates the execution of computationally demanding tasks within tolerable latency. The framework uniquely minimizes task offloading latency and DoA estimation errors by incorporating a novel Nash equilibrium-based reward mechanism.
- **Quantum-Enhanced Actor-Critic Method:** The novel methodology of quantum-enhanced DRL framework, along with actor-critic networks, employs quantum circuits for policy representation and optimization within a multi-agent setting. Demonstrated through extensive simulations, this approach significantly enhances DoA estimation accuracy and task offloading efficiency, meeting URLLC's rigorous demands. The proposed framework fastens the convergence speed during the training process, surpassing the performance of existing conventional DRL-based DDPG [GWF23] and PPO [LZL22] algorithms. The further comparative analysis highlights substantial task offloading latency reductions over traditional DRL algorithms, emphasizing quantum computing's transformative impact on surveillance operations.

8.2 Performance Evaluation

In this section, we provide numerical results to evaluate the performance of the proposed approach. The considered system model is illustrated in Fig. 8.1:

Fig. 8.1: DoA estimation and task offloading using quantum-DRL

The main results of our proposed approach are summarized in Fig. 8.2.

Fig. 8.2: Comparison of RMSE of DoA under various conditions

In Fig. 8.2(a), the efficacy of the quantum-DRL-based RIS phase shift is distinctly evident through the substantial reduction in RMSE for DoA estimation across sensing durations. The proposed approach yields a reduction in RMSE compared to an RIS design with random phase shifts, DDPG, and PPO-based phase shift designs by 94.10%, 91.66%, and 82.61% respectively at a sensing duration of 16 ms. Such efficiency highlights the quantum DRL framework’s superior capability to efficiently explore and optimize the complex, high-dimensional solution space.

Fig. 8.2(b) evaluates the performance of the proposed method against the theoretical lower bound for RMSE in DoA estimation, represented by the CRLB [GWF23]. The reduction in RMSE with the quantum-DRL approach compared to PPO [LZL22] and DDPG [GWF23] methods demonstrates its superior efficiency and closer adherence to the CRLB. The performance gain in RMSE reduction for the quantum-DRL approach compared to the PPO method is approximately 69.16%, and compared to the DDPG method, it is approximately 73.37%, when number of RIS elements is 64. These findings underscore the quantum-DRL framework’s enhanced efficacy in approaching the theoretical accuracy limits set by the CRLB.

In Fig. 8.2(c), the quantum-DRL approach significantly outperforms its relevant benchmarks in reducing the RMSE for DoA estimation. At 5 dB SNR, quantum-DRL reduces the RMSE by approximately 64.59% and 93.23% compared to PPO and DDPG, respectively, showcasing its significant advantage in minimizing estimation errors. This performance highlights quantum-DRL's capabilities in the phase shifts of RIS even in low SNR scenarios, demonstrating its capability for near-theoretical accuracy and robustness to noise.

8.3 Conclusions

We presented a DRL framework to enhance the DoA estimation accuracy and computational task offloading latency in ISAC systems in the presence of RISs. The proposed approach reduces the decision space dimensionality by encoding operational states and actions into quantum states, introducing a quantum-enhanced actor-critic method for policy optimization. Comparative analyses demonstrated significant performance gains, with faster convergence and a 76.32% and 48.73% improvement in normalized reward over DDPG and PPO, respectively. The proposed DRL approach notably reduced the RMSE for DoA estimation by over 94.10% compared to the random phase shift setting, and by 91.66% and 82.61% against DDPG and PPO, respectively. Additionally, the proposed approach minimized task offloading latency under URLLC requirements, achieving up to 43.09% latency reduction compared to DDPG and 32.35% against PPO, evidencing its efficacy.

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